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The Child I Refuse to Outgrow

"Ate, you sound so childish."

Those were the words my sister once said to me. I was a college student at the time, about to graduate. I had been teasing her, and she finally got annoyed. Looking back, I can still laugh about it.

Her comment, however, made me think. Was I really childish? Perhaps I was. I loved laughing, even at the smallest things. A simple joke, an awkward moment, or something completely ordinary could make me burst into laughter. It was not because I was immature or careless. I just found joy in little things.

Then life changed. After graduating from college, I entered the world of work. The transition was not easy. Responsibilities grew heavier, expectations became higher, and reality became more demanding. Slowly, the girl who used to laugh freely began to change. The laughter that once came naturally became less frequent. I became more serious because life itself became serious.

As we grow older, many of us unknowingly trade our childlike wonder for worries. We become occupied with deadlines, bills, responsibilities, and the pressure to succeed. Somewhere along the way, we forget what it feels like to laugh without a reason or to enjoy life without overthinking every step.

Back then, I did not know how to respond. However, if I could answer now, I would tell her, and perhaps everyone else, not to lose that child inside them.

Life will hit us hard. There will be disappointments, failures, and moments when we feel exhausted from carrying burdens we never expected to bear. However, the child within us helps us face those challenges differently. That child reminds us that life is not only a battlefield. It can also be a playground. It teaches us that it is okay to fall, okay to make mistakes, and okay to lose sometimes. Children have a remarkable ability to begin again. They fall, cry for a moment, and then continue playing. As adults, we often forget this simple lesson. We become afraid of failure and too concerned about what others might think. In the process, we lose the courage to enjoy life.

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Many people forget how to laugh, and because of that, they feel old even while they are still young. As another birthday approaches, I often find myself surprised by my age. Truthfully, I do not always feel it. Growing older is not about losing the child within us. However, it is about carrying that child with us as we navigate adulthood. The goal is not to remain childish but to preserve the qualities that make life lighter: curiosity, joy, resilience, and hope.

So, never lose that little child inside you. Laugh at the simple things. Find wonder in ordinary moments. Moreover, whenever you feel like giving up, let the child within you remind you why you started in the first place.